

The conflict in Syria and Turkey's refugee and immigration problem

1. Origin of the Issue and Background

Migration is a phenomenon that has been influenced by all societies throughout human life. There is an ongoing social mobility in the world due to reasons such as wars, exiles, hunger, financial difficulties and disasters. Hence, it is as old as history.

According to the perspective of modern history, it is impossible to imagine the development of capitalism without including immigration. Simply expressed, waves of migration from the rural to the city were made possible by the release of the peasants who had been bound to the land by the feudal system of Western Europe and the acceleration of urbanization with industrialization. The movement of qualified workers from nations like the Netherlands to nations like Germany and England during the Mercantilist period, which spanned the 16th and 18th centuries, was one of the reasons that helped to spark the industrial revolutions. The colonialism wave that began in the 15th century is another movement that helped pave the way for the industrial revolution. A massive wave of forced migration from Africa to the Americas also made it possible for capitalism to go worldwide and enter the imperialist stage. Finally, it may be claimed that comprehending capitalism without also understanding the phenomena of global migration is impossible (Pincus, 2009).

Immigration is the international movement of people to a destination country of which they are not natives or where they do not possess citizenship in order to settle as permanent residents or naturalized citizens (Oxford Dictionaries, 2013). In the 17th century, the phrase "immigration" was first used to describe non-combative (non-warlike) population transfers among the newly formed nation states. From the perspective of the destination country, when people migrate across borders, they are referred to as migrants or immigrants (from the Latin migrare, "wanderer"). From the perspective of the nation they are leaving, however, they are referred to as emigrants or outmigrants.

By 2020, it is seen that the number of "immigrants" who do not live in their own country in the world almost approaches 300 million. As it is clearly seen in the table below, the number of international immigrants has increased 4 times in the last 50 years.

Figure 1. Number and Share of Global Migrants, 1960-2020

Source: (Batalova, 2022)

In the definition of international migration, the concept of "asylum seeker" refers to people who seek international protection as a refugee, but whose social status has not been formalized. In this case, foreign persons who are not officially refugees continue their existence in the country temporarily within the framework of the special laws of the states. While the number of international asylum seekers was 14 million in 2000, it has reached historical levels with a population of 26.4 million as of 2020.

A similar record was reached by the 55 million individuals who were internally displaced due to calamities and armed war in just 2020. The startling statistics mentioned above, according to the United Nations 2022 World Migration Report, demonstrate that the combined impact of geopolitical, environmental, and economic issues has grown to a size that cannot be ignored. (Marie McAuliffe & Anna Triandafyllidou, 2022).

Of course, the "uneven development" helped bring about by the imperialist-capitalist system includes the global immigration issue as well. The world system, according to Immanuel Wallerstein, is a socioeconomic structure built on uneven trade between "core and periphery" nations. The idea of "unequal exchange," which is key to this definition, describes the profit-transfer that occurs when surplus value produced in peripheral regions is unfairly transferred to core countries (Wallerstein, 2000). As a result, this unequal exchange also appears in international migration movements. Today, half of all immigrants immigrate to the USA and Europe. According to Wallerstein's theory, the skilled labor force, which is dissatisfied due to the uneven development and negative living conditions in the peripheral countries, tends to brain drain towards the core countries, and this phenomenon leads to a significant loss of qualifications in the peripheral countries. Unqualified segments of the workforce may also migrate to core countries as refugees for similar reasons.

In this article, the situation in Syria due to US imperialism with the "civil war" that started in Syria in 2011 will be examined and the Syrian refugee problem in Turkey as a result.

2. Conflict in Syria

In its simplest and basic form, imperialism can be defined as a set of structural relations that enable the worldwide organization of capitalist exploitation and oppression in the division of labor across nations. It is an advanced stage of the globalization of capitalism. Of course, certain nations that assert hegemony or leadership take the lead in the organization of the economic, military, and cultural relations that shape imperialism in addition to multinational corporations. The hegemonic nations, which are the political epicenter of monopoly capital at the top, are requested to maintain the technological, political, ideological, and cultural identity and continuity of this control, as well as the control of natural resources, labor, and other forms of wealth. (Gürçan, 2021).

The famous American political scientist F. Fukuyama proposed the argument that the fall of the USSR marked the "End of History"(Francis Fukuyama, 1989). This ideology held that the United States and "liberal democracy" had won, and that the world order should now be based on them and be "unipolar".

According to that theory, the USA launched the Gulf War after 1991, NATO intervened in the situation in Bosnia, and the breakup of Yugoslavia quickened. The US was not satisfied with these and declared war on Afghanistan in 2001 at the beginning of the 21st century, followed by a second invasion of Iraq two years later. It is a well-known fact that during this period, the USA had a change of power in Latin America, Africa and the Middle East, with the help of the CIA, military coups or assassinations. (*The Untold History of the United States*, 2012).

In 2011, civil war broke out in Syria. But many facts showed that the US had triggered the war. So much so that the former US President Donald Trump said that Obama is the founder of the ISIS, which is one of the biggest actors of the civil war in Syria (politico.eu, 2016). It is an obvious fact that the PYD, the Syrian branch of the PKK terrorist organization, which declared "autonomy" in large settlements such as Kobani, Qamishli and Afrin in northern Syria, also carries out military operations in Syria with the support of the USA (Vakkas Doğantekin, 2019).

The military intervention of the USA and its Western allies in Syria, taking advantage of the "Arab Spring" environment, dragged the country into a proxy war. Ultimately, it is estimated that 13.5 million people, in other words, more than half of the country's population, have been forced to migrate for the reasons listed above. The number of people forced to migrate in the world has reached 82.4 million by 2021. Syrians forced to migrate alone constitute more than 16% of this population. It is estimated that the total number of asylum seekers has reached 26.4 million these days, when we are experiencing the largest refugee wave in history since World War II. Syrian refugees, on the other hand, represent a significant part of the world's refugee population with 6.7 million. (UNHCR - Refugee Statistics, 2022).

The USA has produced chaos, terror and instability in every country and region it has interfered directly or indirectly. Naturally, this process, with its political consequences, directly interfered with the socio-economic processes, life, education life, housing situation and overall order of tens of millions of people. If people pay close attention, the main nations that are discussed when it comes to the refugee crisis are Syria, Iraq, and Afghanistan, which are the direct targets of the United States. It is hard to think about the issue of global migration and asylum seekers in this context without taking the United States

into consideration. The Republic of Turkey's Minister of Interior, Süleyman Soyly, stated in a speech on April 13, 2022, "For the first time in history, in an age when civilization was purportedly at its most evolved, the issue of migration has developed into a worldwide disaster like never before witnessed in history. He stated that "Western imperialism laid the stones of migrant pathways," which served as the primary cause of the issue. (sputniknews.com, 2022).

3. The imperialist intervention in the Middle East and the migration crisis in Turkey

The phenomenon of international migration is of great concern to Turkey as the country with the world's largest refugee population with a number of approximately 4 million (World Bank, 2021). The number of irregular migrants in Turkey increased from 32,667 in 2010 to 454,662 in 2019 with an increase of approximately 1292%. The number of asylum seekers in Turkey, estimated at around 989,000 in January 2010, has increased by more than 304% by 2021. It is estimated that 3.6 million of the 4 million refugees are Syrians, and the majority of the rest are Afghans. In addition, according to the data of the Ministry of Interior of the Republic of Turkey, more than 2.5 million irregular migrants were not allowed to enter the country in the last 6 years (İçişleri Bakanlığı Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı, 2022).

It is not a coincidence that Afghanistan and Syria come to the fore in the historical refugee problem in Turkey. The 20-year war directly waged by the United States in Afghanistan, the devastation caused by the 11-year war it indirectly continued in Syria, and the refugee crisis have a very negative impact on Turkey. The Syrian crisis has hosted the most serious humanitarian crisis since World War II. Today, this wave of crisis is expanding to Afghanistan. In addition hand, given its accessibility to Europe within the context of the mentioned migration wave, Turkey has a important location that immigrants prefer highly. Afghanistan is the second-largest sending country in the world, after Syria, with 2.6 million refugees in 2020 alone. With 3.5 million internally displaced people, Afghanistan ranks fifth in the world in terms of this statistic. This nation is one of the top ten nations in the world with more than 5 million immigrants, according to the 2022 World Migration Report (Marie McAuliffe & Anna Triandafyllidou, 2022).

Figure 2. Refugees in Turkey

Source: (Gibárti, 2021)

4. How Turkey is handling the migration and refugee crises?

Giving official refugee status for the Syrian refugees in Turkey was hindered by the fact that Ankara did not lift the geographical restrictions in the Geneva Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees of 1951 and its Protocol of 1967. Under this clause, only citizens of the Council of Europe member states are eligible for official refugee status in Turkey.

This geographical restriction, by definition, precludes the granting of official refugee status to refugees or stateless persons from Syria – and other countries in the Middle East or Africa. It is important to highlight that previous legal documents aimed at addressing the shortcomings of the Geneva Convention have not proved to be sufficient to deal with the intensifying influx of refugees from Syria.

As the number of refugees increased, the Turkish government also adapted a relevant institutional framework for the changing circumstances. One of the most critical changes in the institutional system was the establishment of the Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) under the Ministry of Interior in 2013. The Directorate is responsible for implementing all government policies related to migration, including policies with temporary protection status for stateless persons and victims of human trafficking.

The Turkish authorities initially sheltered refugees in refugee camps along the southeastern border of the country. However, the capacity of the camps could not keep pace with the steady increase in the number of refugees. As a result, the proportion of in-camp refugees has declined significantly over the years: while the proportion of people living in camps was 12% in 2015 (World Bank, 2015), according to DGMM, the same proportion did not reach 3% in 2020 (Directorate General of Migration Management, Ministry of Interior, Republic of Turkey, 2022). So, more than 97% of the Syrian refugees live in urban areas of Turkey, mostly in southeastern provinces (Gaziantep, Hatay, or Şanlıurfa) and the metropolitan area of Istanbul (see the Map below).

Figure 3. Provincial breakdown of Syrians with Temporary Protection Status

Source: (Gibárti, 2021)

5. International Response

At the time of the first major influx of refugees, Turkey began resettling the incoming Syrians in camps at the Turkish-Syrian border as well as started providing different forms of humanitarian assistance to them.

After the intensely growing flow of refugees from 2012, the Turkish government decided to alter its original policies and approved the operations of UN agencies, while it has also initiated tighter partnerships with international actors in humanitarian assistance (UNICEF, 2015).

As mentioned above, the widespread and protracted refugee crises and the specific situation of Turkey have prompted the UN and its humanitarian

agencies to rethink their humanitarian aid policies and to set up context-specific programs.

Turkey started the Emergency Social Safety Net Program (ESSN), as the main form of international assistance in Turkey. The ESSN Program launched in November 2016 was funded by the European Commission and implemented by the World Food Program and the Turkish Red Crescent to assist the most vulnerable refugees with high levels of food insecurity and extreme poverty. It is important to highlight that as the whole Syria Regional Response Plan framework does, the program operates through the Turkish government and the social welfare system with the help of important government stakeholders.

The ESSN aims to tackle the most urgent humanitarian challenges of Syrian refugees in Turkey with multi-purpose, unrestricted, and unconditional cash assistance on a debit card by monthly donations. This relief method is regarded as an innovative approach to dealing with the urgent humanitarian needs of Syrian refugees in Turkey and is often cited as the largest humanitarian aid program in the world for assisting forcibly displaced people (Turkish Red Crescent, 2020). It is innovative in the sense that cash-based assistance is considered a highly inventive form of humanitarian relief, as it encourages the people that are benefitting to choose and decide what goods they need the most.

6. Conclusion

The most fundamental and determining factor leading to international migration movements is capitalism and its historical transformation. The most defining feature of capitalism today is "imperialism". The international dimensions of migration in modern times cannot be properly understood without taking into account imperialism.

The imperialist intervention and proxy wars in Syria since 2011 have triggered one of the biggest humanitarian crises since World War II.

Every nation and region the USA has directly or indirectly entered has suffered chaos, terror, and instability as a result. It is undeniable that this process and its political implications directly impacted the socioeconomic processes, daily lives, educational experiences, housing conditions, and overall social order of tens of millions of people. If one pays attention, the main nations discussed in the

refugee issue are Syria, Iraq, and Afghanistan, which are the direct targets of the United States.

The Syrian refugee problem is essentially a problem initiated by imperialism by attacking Syria. In order to solve the problem, first of all, the US troops must be withdrawn from Syria. Establishing peace in Syria is the most important step.

Turkey, on the other hand, should start official high level diplomatic contacts with the Syrian government again and strive for the return of Syrian citizens to their countries.

The primary condition for the safe return of Syrians is to ensure the territorial integrity of Syria. If Turkey agrees with Syria, PKK-YPG and terrorist organizations under the control of the USA will be cleared, the USA will leave Syria, thus creating a suitable environment for the Syrians to return to their homes.

The Syrian government has declared a "general amnesty" many times and invites its citizens abroad to their countries. In order to reduce the negative effects of the war in Syria, it is necessary to create international solidarity.

The capitalist-imperialist system's underlying tensions are becoming more pronounced in the 2000s. The current economic crisis is becoming more severe, and when combined with the military, environmental, and agricultural crises, it poses a threat to not only capitalism but to all of humanity. The international migration problem, which has gained attention in recent years, especially after 2010, is a crucial component of this process and is becoming more serious as it comes into contact with crises in the economy, military, environment, and agriculture. This article examines the connection between imperialism and global migration in light of all these realities.

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